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Research Article

Reasons and Determinants for Attending Primary Health Care Centers among Adults, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia 2018

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Abstract:

Background: Primary health care represents the first contact of an individual and families with the healthcare system and is a major part of the many initiatives of the Ministry of Health (MOH) that are directed towards the national transformation plan 2020 and the Saudi vision 2030. It is of vast importance to determine the reasons for attending primary health care centers for identification and meeting the health needs of studied population.

Objective: The aim of this study is to identify reasons for attending primary health care centers among adults in Jeddah City.

Methods: A cross sectional survey comprising 451 (225 males (49.9%) and 226 females (50.1%)) adults, visiting 9 primary health care centers. These PHCCs were selected from each health sector in Jeddah city using proportional allocation technique. Furthermore systematic random sampling was utilized to select participants from each PHCC. Participants were invited to complete a 19 item interviewed questionnaire which consists of three parts: socio-demographic data, past medical history and identifying the reason for attendance. These questionnaires were collected within a period of one month from November 2018 to January 2019.

Results: Fifty six percent of the study population attended PHCs for health problems and the remainder attended for health services. The most common reason for attendance was respiratory system complaints followed by medication refill service. The most common chronic diseases encountered were diabetes and hypertension

Conclusion: Respiratory complaints followed by dental care and womens' health issues account for the most common reason for PHCCs attendance and further action should be implemented based on these findings to ensure adequate care of PHCCs attenders.

Key Words: Primary health care; Public health; Health services.

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INTRODUCTION:**BACKGROUND:**

The Saudi Primary Health Care Centers (PHCCs) are offering comprehensive care for every Saudi citizen which includes health promotion services in the form of health education and immunization for everybody.¹ Primary health care represents the first contact of an individual and families with the healthcare system as a whole.² Primary health care is the cornerstone of the Saudi health system and is a major part of the many initiatives of the Ministry of Health (MOH) that are directed towards the national transformation plan 2020 and the Saudi vision 2030.³

According to the Health profile of Saudi Arabia by World Health Organization (WHO) published in the year 2015, the burden of disease attributable to non-communicable diseases is 78%, leading them; cardiovascular diseases followed by cancers, respiratory diseases, and diabetes mellitus.⁴ In 2017, the Saudi General Authority for Statistics released the annual population estimates report and estimated that the Saudi population reached 32 million.⁵ Over 8 million individuals of different nationalities, Saudi and non-Saudi, reside in Makkah Province where Jeddah city falls in.⁶ A total of 101 governmental PHCCs services Jeddah city.⁷

It is of vast importance to determine the reasons for attending primary health care centers for identification and meeting the health needs in the studied population.⁸ It was also suggested that interventions directed towards primary health care might reduce the frequency of uncalled for visitations to emergency department.⁹

The identification of reasons for attendance among adults visiting PHCCs will aid in properly using the resources in like manner of the stocking of needed medications, improving chronic clinics and may lead to the lessening of hospitalization and emergency rooms crowding.^{9,10} This Furthermore, may help in aiding and guiding primary care practitioners.¹¹

The reasons for attending PHCCs may be strictly medical or non-medical. Even in the clear medical reasons obtaining a unified classification in literature was difficult. There are a few used classifications, not limited to; the Johns Hopkins Adjusted Clinical Groups (ACG) which classifies the patient being the subject rather than the disease nor the symptoms,^{10,12} unlike; the International Classification of Primary Care-2 (ICPC-2) which is mapped to ICD system.^{10,11,14,15}

Of the many characteristics of the ICPC-2, the following may be the most applicable in primary care settings; the reference of 17 chapters of body systems portraying the localization of the problem and disease, with it a chapter for general and unspecified issues, and a chapter for social problems.”¹⁶ The mentioned classifications although similar in purpose, they are mostly distinct, making the study of reasons for attending PHCCs an extraordinary task. There are limited studies addressing the reasons for PHCCs attendance in the adult population that were carried out in the kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and none were conducted in Jeddah city.

It was concluded in the studies of both developed & developing countries, that respiratory diseases were the main reason for PHCCs attendance. ^{8,11,12,14,15, 17} A study conducted by Al-Eissa, 18 years back, in the capital, Riyadh city among adolescents, concluded that the trend of reasons and morbidities were those similar to developed countries.¹⁸ Another study carried out in Makkah, targeting pilgrims during the Hajj season, also concluded that the most commonly occurring diseases were those of the respiratory system.¹⁹

RATIONALE:

The identification of reasons for attending PHCCs is of immense importance for the Saudi health care system. Providing vital information for providers and policymakers for planning purposes. The PHCCs are the gate to the health care system; it serves every Saudi citizen, obtaining the reason for approaching the gate would mainly impact its' services.

As family medicine residents, amid the journey of specializing and learning the broad scope of primary care, it is essential that one's interest is directed by the needs of her/his community to more narrow scope to be better equipped for practice.

The Aim Of The Study:

The general aim of this study is to identify reasons for attending primary health care centers among adults.

OBJECTIVES:

1. To identify the reasons for attending the Ministry of Health primary health care centers among adults, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia, 2018
2. To identify the determinants associated with reasons for attending the Ministry of Health primary health care centers in Jeddah, during the study period.

METHODS:

Study Design: The study design was cross-sectional. The study was carried out based on primary care attendees, using a validated questionnaire; data were collected from nine urban PHCCs.

Study Area: The study location was Jeddah city. Jeddah is located in the western province of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, in the province of Makkah which has a population of eight million. The Ministry of Health provides primary health care through 2282 centers that widely distributed across the country. This study was carried out in nine PHCCs randomly selected from a total of 47 urban PHCCs serving Jeddah city. These 47 urban PHCCs are distributed into five health sectors based on the tertiary health care facilities, 11 are affiliated to King Abdullah Medical Complex, 13 are affiliated to King Fahd General Hospital, ten are affiliated to East Jeddah Hospital, seven and 13 PHCCs are affiliated to King Abdulaziz Hospital and Al Thaghr Hospital respectively.

Study Population: Adult patients attending the Ministry of Health PHCCs in November 2018 to January 2019.

Inclusion criteria: All PHCCs adult patients who were present during the study period were eligible to be included in the study. Individuals aged 15 years and older were considered as adults according to the Islamic definition of Adulthood

Exclusion criteria:

1. Non-consenting individuals
2. Individuals who are unable to respond either due to medical or non-medical conditions.
3. Persons who attended PHCCs as caregiver or patient escort.

Sample Size: By using Roasoft calculator, the Sample size was calculated with the following criteria:

Error: 5%

Confidence level: 95%

The prevalence of the problem: 50%

Population size: 20000

The calculated sample size is 377 increased by 20% to be 451; to account for non-respondents.

Sampling technique: The PHCCs were stratified according to the MOH five health sectors. The proportional allocation technique was utilized to select one or more PHCCs from each health sector according to the number of PHCCs in each sector. The calculated sample size from each PHCC was around 50 participants. Systematic random sample technique was

used to select participants from each PHCC and to ensure that fair samples of males and females were selected, 25 participants from each sex category were included.

Data collection tool: The researchers designed a questionnaire, especially for this study. The questionnaire was validated and used for data collection. (Annexure i). The questionnaire consists of three parts: socio-demographic data, past medical history and identifying the reason for attendance.

Validity of questionnaire: The questionnaire was validated in English and Arabic versions. Since the researcher constructed the questionnaire, it was validated by three experts and was pretested as well. (Annexure ii)

Data Collection technique: During their visits to the PHCCs and after being triaged. The researchers themselves interviewed each participants using the validated questionnaire.

After data collection, the medical reason for attendance as stated by the study participants during the interview were mapped and classified based on ICPC-2 and charted in the corresponding Excel data sheet.

The ICPC has a biaxial structure and consists of 17 chapters, each divided into seven components. Component one in each was followed since it is dealing with symptoms and complaints. Component one comprises the symptoms and illnesses, which portray the localization of it to a specific body part. (Annexure iii) For example, ICPC-E translates into Ear and comprises of ear pain, ear discharge.

Pretesting: A pilot study was carried out on a sample of 10% of the total sample size (N=50) and was conducted in a PHCC other than those selected for the study. Participants included in the pilot study were excluded the pilot study aimed to assess validity, clarity & feasibility the questionnaire from the study.

Study Time: Data collection was carried out between October 2018 and January 2019. The time setting of interviews was during the working hours of the PHCCs from 8:00 am to 4:00 PM.

Study Procedures: Since there are five health care sectors in Jeddah city, one or more PHCCs from each health sector were selected randomly, using online-generated random numbers.

Study variables: Dependent variable: Reason for attending PHCC in that day: Symptom, Follow up,

Immunization, Health Education, Dental Care, Social Issues.

Independent variables: Age, Gender, Marital Status, Occupation, Level of Education, Income, Diabetes, Hypertension, Dyslipidemia, Bronchial Asthma, Thyroid Disease, being a current or past smoker, Nationality, Type of Service at PHCC.

Data Entry And Analysis: The collected data was analyzed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 22. A descriptive and analytical test was appropriately utilized after data collection and entry. Significance: P-value < 0.05 was considered significant.

Ethical considerations: The research proposal and questionnaire were approved by the joined program of family medicine postgraduate studies and research committee. Public health administration approval was obtained as well before the patient interview is carried out.

Consents: Written consents from all participants were obtained prior to the interview, and for individuals

aged 15 to less than 18 was obtained from the guardian.

Privacy and confidentiality: All information obtained during the study was kept confidential. An identification number was assigned to each participant. Participants' personal information will not be used in any reports, presentations or publications. If the results of this study are published, participants will not be identified in any way.

Budget: This was a self-funded research and author declares no conflict of interest.

RESULTS:

Sociodemographic Characteristics of the study population: Of the 451 participants in the study, Saudi nationality represents the majority 83%. Males and Females were equally distributed 50%, 72% of the participants were married, and 8% of the females were pregnant. One hundred and ninety-nine (44%) were in the age-group more than 35 to 55 years, 206 (46%) were unemployed. Out of the 190 (42%) who were employed; 27 (14%) were housemaids. The participants were almost equally distributed regarding their education levels. The monthly income of 158 (35%) was less than 5000 SAR (Table 1).

Table 1: Socio-demographic profile of the study population according to the study location.

Character	N (%)
Nationality	
Saudi	376 (83.4)
Non-Saudi	75 (16.6)
Marital Status	
Married	322 (71.4)
Single	128 (28.4)
Missing data	1 (0.2)
Gender	
Male	225 (49.9)
Female	226 (50.1)
Age group	
15-35	146 (36.4)
>35-55	199 (44.1)
>55	88 (19.2)
Monthly Income	
<5000	158 (35.0)
>5000-10000	127 (28.2)
>10000-15000	80 (17.7)
>15000-20000	36 (8.0)
>20000	50 (11.1)
Occupation	
Student	51 (11.3)
Employed	194 (43)
Unemployed	206 (45.7)
Education category	

Below secondary school	134 (29.7)
Secondary school & above	142 (33.7)
Bachelor's degree & above	165 (36.6)
Total	451

Participants' status in PHCCs and comorbidities pattern: Most of the participants have active medical records in PHCCs 89%, while 98% reside in Jeddah city. The most common chronic diseases in the study population were diabetes, and the least common was thyroid diseases (Figure 1). Twenty-one percent of the participants were current smokers.

Figure 1: Percentages of chronic diseases in the study population

Reasons for attending PHCCs in study population:

More than half of the study population, 253 (56%) attended PHCCs because of health problems, while the rest 198 (44%) attended for the sake of health services. Out of the total study population, only 14 (3%) stated that their main reason for attendance was a sick-leaves request.

By further categorizing of health problems using ICPC-2 symptoms/complaints body systems categorization, the top five health problems presenting to studied PHCCs were respiratory 79 (31.2%) followed by dental 40 (15.8%), female genital 32 (12.6%), general & unspecified 26 (10.3%), and musculoskeletal 24 (9.5%) (Figure 2).

Health services were also categorized using ICPC-2 process codes, medication refill 38.9% was the top reason, followed by blood test requests and follow up visits 14% for each one (Table 2).

In all age groups, the most common reason for attending PHCCs was health services followed by respiratory complaints except for the age group 15-35 years; where respiratory complaints and health services have the same frequency of 23.8% followed by female genital complaints 14% and dental health 11% (Table 3).

Medication refill was most utilized by 54% of the age-group 35-55 years followed by more than 55-75 age-group and older 38.2% and least utilized by the age-group 15-35 years 7.9%.

Cardiovascular diseases and ear complaints were solely observed in the age-group 35-55 years. Skin, urological, female genital and digestive complaints were also not observed in the age group 55-75 years and older. Digestive and female genital complaints were more common the age group 15-35 years, 88.9% and 71.9% respectively.

Figure 2: Reasons for Attending PHCCs by Health-problems in study population using ICPC-2

Table 2: Reasons for Attending PHCCs by Health services in study population using ICPC-2 process codes

Health Service	N (%)
Medication refill	77 (38.9)
Blood test	28 (14.1)
Follow up	28 (14.1)
Results test	17 (8.6)
Administrative procedure	13 (6.6)
Referral to specialist/hospital	13 (6.6)
Preventive immunization	11 (5.6)
Health evaluation	6 (3)
Local injection/Dressing	4 (2)
Urine test	1 (0.5)
Total	198 (100)

Table 3: Reasons for Attending PHCCs by age group in the study population using ICPC-2 body systems.

REASONS	AGE-GROUPS			TOTAL
	15-35	>35-55	>55-75	
Respiratory	39	32	8	79
Dental	18	17	5	40
Female genital	23	9	0	32
General & Unspecified	12	10	4	26
Musculoskeletal	4	12	8	24
TOTAL	96	80	25	201

Determinants for reasons for attending PHCCs: There was a statistically significant difference regarding reasons for PHCCs attendance; health services and health problems; according to the following variables, sex, age-groups, job-categories, educational level, nationality, diabetes, hypertension, hyperlipidemia, thyroid diseases, and bronchial asthma. On the other hand, pregnancy, marital status, monthly income, Bronchial asthma, smoking found to be statistically not significant (Tables 4 and 5).

Table 4: Reasons for PHCCs attendance with a statistically significant difference.

Character	Health service		p-value, OR (95% CI)
	H. problems N (%)	H. Services N (%)	
Nationality			
Saudi	221	155	0.01 , 0.72 (0.57-0.9)
Non-Saudi	32	43	
Gender			
Male	114	111	0.02, 1,28 (1,04-1.58)
Female	139	87	
Age-groups			
15-35	119	45	0.0005
>35-55	104	95	
>55	30	58	
Job categories			
Student	37	14	0.04
Worker	106	88	
no job	110	96	
Education Level			
Below secondary school	64	70	0.032
Secondary school & above	96	56	
Bachelor's degree & above	93	72	
Diabetes			
Yes	29	95	0.0005,2.4 (2.02-2.9)
No	224	103	
Hypertension			
Yes	31	77	0.0005,2.02(1.68-2.4)
No	222	121	
Hyperlipidemia			
Yes	20	72	0.0005,2.2 (1.9-2.7)
No	233	126	
Thyroid Diseases			
Yes	9	21	0.003 ,1.67 (1.28-2.16)
No	244	176	

Table 5: Reasons for PHCCs attendance with no statistically significant difference.

Character	Health service		p-value, OR (95% CI)
	H. problems N (%)	H. Services N (%)	
Monthly Income			
<5000	82	76	0.232
>5000-10000	77	50	
>10000-15000	51	29	
>15000-20000	19	17	
>20000	24	26	
Pregnancy			
Yes	14	4	0.088, 0.52 (0.22-1.249)
No	116	87	
Smoking			
Yes	53	41	0.95 , 1.006 (0.82-1.23)
No	200	157	
Marital Status			
Married	175	147	0.20, 0.86 (0.67-1.09)
Single	78	50	
Bronchial Asthma			
Yes	53	41	0.56, 1.116 (.780-1.597)
No	200	157	

All factors in the bivariate analysis were entered for stepwise logistic regression analysis. The total number of unweighted cases was 451. Dependent Variable "reasons for attendance" encoding was 0 for a health problem and 1 for health service. The overall percentage of correctly classified cases without any predictor variables in the model (Block 0 section) was 59.4% which improved with entering the predictors in the model to 71.7%. Hosmer and Lemeshow Test showed that the model is useful (Chi-square 3.4; df; 4 p-values 0.355). The model can predict 20% to 27% of the variation of the dependent variable (The Cox & Snell R square =0,20 and Nagelkerke R Square = 0.27). Factors that retained significance were the nationality of the participants, having diabetes, thyroid diseases, or hyperlipidemia (Table 6).

Table 6: Logistic Regression analysis: Odd of the type of service=Health service

Variables	Crude p-value; OR (95% CI)	Adjusted p-value; OR (95% CI)
Nationality	0.01 , 1.38 (1.05-1.82)	0.04, 0.45 (0.204-0.978)
Saudi		
Non-Saudi		
Diabetes	0.005, 0.34 (0.25-0.47)	0.002, 3.97 (1.67-9.44)
Yes		
No		
hyperlipidemia	0.020, 0.34(0.23-0.50)	0.02, 2.99 (1.19-7.52)
Yes		
No		
Thyroid disease	0.003, 0.52 (0.30-0.90)	0.001, 0.179 (0.06-0.51)
Yes		
No		

DISCUSSION:

Up to researchers' knowledge and literature review dated March 2018, this is the first study conducted in Saudi Arabia that is addressing the reasons for attending PHCCs among adults using ICPC-2 classification system. All of the 451 interviewed patients responded to all questions, except for one patient who did not respond to the questions referring to marital and thyroid status; which were considered missed data and included in the statistical analysis.

The most frequent health problems in the study population were problems of the respiratory system, which is similar to studies conducted in Malaysia, Sri Lanka and India. 14,15, 20 The frequency of the problems of the respiratory system in this study was (31.2%) concordant to Sri Lanka study (31.8%), but higher than Malaysia study (18%). This finding differences may be due to the difference in timing of data collection which was carried in winter months. Moreover, when comparing to POSIDEN, a study which was conducted in India with a sample size of more than 200,000 participants, 1-day point-prevalence study across 880 Indian cities, the frequency of respiratory illnesses was 50%, could be due to difference in climate between the two countries or due to the difference in the nature of participants where they included pediatric age-group in their study.

According to the Global Burden of Disease Report in 2013, the second most common leading cause of death in India was respiratory. Besides, Duong et al. (ref) ranked India as the lowest lung function of the 17 countries that were included in their study.

The second most prevalent diseases were those of the gastrointestinal system, in contrast to our study which showed that dental health was the second and the digestive was not from the top five reasons for attending PHCCs, this difference could be explained by the difference in study population where they included pediatric age-group in their study.

Other aspects of studies were not comparable may be due to the utilization of a different categorization system for diagnosis and the nature of participants and study designs.

In the current study, only 1.3% of the participants presented for health evaluation which is comparable to the Malaysian study and Aleissa study conducted in Saudi Arabia in the year 2000.

The frequency of pregnancy was 8%, which is lower than other studies carried out in different parts of Asia.

This difference could be related to the current health policies implemented in PHCCs in Saudi Arabia, where only three essential visits are scheduled in the antenatal care programs of PHCCs. However, it is higher than that observed in Aleissa study 3% which included the adolescent population only.

It is interesting that psychological and social problems were not observed as one of the major reasons for attending PHCCs, 0.4%, this could be due to decrease awareness in the community, and health care providers about the role of PHCCs in managing such cases or the unavailability of social workers and psychiatric medications in some of the studied PHCCs. A similar statement was mentioned by Aleissa study where the percentage of psychiatric illnesses was 0.2% only.

Sick-leave request as the main reason for attending PHCCs was only 3% in the current study, resembling the results of Aleissa study.

Regarding the attendance for immunization services, Aleissa reported a percentage of 0.2, while in the current study the percentage was 5.6. This difference in the percentages of the attendance for immunization services is expected as a result of the application of new policies regarding adult immunization¹⁸.

LIMITATION:

The nature of the study being a cross-sectional study in a point of time may affected the reasons and determinants for attending PHCCs. The usage of the ICPC-2 classification system in a paper-based method since the interviews were carried out before implementation of new electronic filing systems that were started in March 2019, may also have neglected possible hidden agendas such as requesting sickleaves and referrals.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, Respiratory complaints and dental care were identified as the most frequent health problems as reasons to visit the PHCCs in Jeddah city while medication refill being the reason for attendance was the most utilized health service. On the other hand psychological complaints & preventive health services were among the least encountered reasons for attendance in the study population, which may suggest inadequate level of awareness about availability of these health services in the PHCCs.

RECOMMENDATION:

1. Awareness and knowledge about PHCCs services should be further studied to determine the user and community perceptions and information need in target population about available health resources.
2. Role of nonpharmacological and self-management of upper respiratory tract disease should be more emphasized among community.
3. Increase awareness about availability of uncommonly used health care services such as psychology and Health maintenance/prevention.
4. Implementation of automatic medication refill for stable chronic disease patients.

REFERENCES

1. Al-Khaldi YM, Al-Ghamdi EA, Al-Mogbil TI, Al-Khashan HI. Family medicine practice in Saudi Arabia: The current situation and Proposed Strategic Directions Plan 2020. *J Family Community Med.* 2017;24(3):156-63.
2. Donaldson MS, Yordy KD, Lohr KN, Vanselow NA, editors. *Primary care: America's health in a new era.* National Academies Press; 1996 Sep 19.
3. MOH Team. The MOH Initiatives Related to the NTP 2020 and Saudi Vision 2030 [Internet]. *Moh.gov.sa.* 2017 [cited 26 March 2018]. Available from: <https://www.moh.gov.sa/en/Ministry/nehs/Pages/vision2030.aspx>
4. Saudi Arabia health profile 2015 [Internet]. WHO. 2015 [cited 26 March 2018]. Available from: http://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/253771/EMROPUB_2016_EN_19272.pdf?sequence=1
5. General Authority of Statistics Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. [Internet]. 2018 [cited 21 March 2018]. Available from: <https://www.stats.gov.sa/>
6. Population Characteristics surveys [Internet]. *Stats.gov.sa.* 2017 [cited 26 March 2018]. Available from: https://www.stats.gov.sa/sites/default/files/population_characteristics_surveysar.pdf ربط 47 مركزا صحيفة البلاد. 2017. صحيفه البلاد. [Internet]. 2017. صحيفه البلاد. [cited 26 March 2018]. Available from: <http://www.goo.gl/GD8fHJ>
7. Wändell P, Carlsson AC, Wettermark B, Lord G, Cars T, Ljunggren G. Most common diseases diagnosed in primary care in Stockholm, Sweden, in 2011. *FamPract.* 2013;30(5):506-13.
8. Alghanim SA, Alomar BA. Frequent use of emergency departments in Saudi public hospitals: implications for primary health care services. *Asia Pac J Public Health.* 2015;27(2):NP2521-30.
9. Carretero MT, Calderón-Larrañaga A, Poblador-Plou B, Prados-Torres A. Primary health care use from the perspective of gender and morbidity burden. *BMC Women's Health.* 2014;14:145.
10. Mash B, Fairall L, Adejayan O, Ikpefan O, Kumari J, Mathee S, et al. A morbidity survey of South African primary care. *PLoS One.* 2012;7(3):e32358.
11. Carlsson L, Strender LE, Fridh G, Nilsson G. Types of morbidity and categories of patients in a Swedish county. Applying the Johns Hopkins Adjusted Clinical Groups System
12. Depolo T, Džono A, John O, Curlin M. Morbidity trends registered in Croatian family practice in the period 1995-2012. *CollAntropol.* 2014;38Suppl 2:25-30.
13. Mimi O, Tong S, Nordin S, Teng C, Khoo E, Abdul-Rahman A, et al. A comparison of morbidity patterns in public and private primary care clinics in Malaysia. *Malays Fam Physician.* 2011;6 (1):19-25.
14. Salvi S, Apte K, Madras S, Barne M, Chhowala S, Sethi T, et al. Symptoms and medical conditions in 204 912 patients visiting primary health-care practitioners in India: a 1-day point prevalence study (the POSEIDON study). *Lancet Glob Health.* 2015;3(12):e776-84.
15. Global Family Doctor - WONCA Online [Internet]. *Globalfamilydoctor.com.* 2018 [cited 26 March 2018]. Available from: <http://www.globalfamilydoctor.com/groups/WorkingParties/wicc.aspx>
16. Annual number and percent distribution of ambulatory care visits by setting type according to diagnosis group [Internet]. *Cdc.gov.* 2010 [cited 26 March 2018]. Available from: https://www.cdc.gov/nchs/data/ahcd/combined_tables/2009-2010_combined_web_table01.pdf
17. Al-Eissa EI. The morbidity pattern among adolescents visiting primary health care centers. *Saudi Med J.* 2000;21 (10):934-7. Alzahrani AG, Choudhry AJ, Al Mazroa MA, Turkistani AH, Nouman GS, Memish ZA.
18. The pattern of diseases among visitors to Mina health centers during the Hajj season, 1429 H (2008 G). *J Infect Public Health.* 2012;5 (1):22-34.